

Euphresco

Final project report

Project title (Acronym)

***Phytophthora* in public gardens: understanding pathways and mitigating risk
(Phyto-gard)**

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2. Short project report

2.1. Short Executive summary

Diseases caused by invasive *Phytophthora* pathogens have significantly affected forest and natural ecosystems worldwide. The introduction and spread of new and/or regulated species has had negative impacts on the environment and on timber industries. A recent study suggests that the invasive *P. ramorum*, introduced to Europe in the mid-1990s, has potential to cause direct damage costs of €117 million for larch and €130 million for beech if not managed (Kartakis et al., 2026). The role of the plant trade in introducing and spreading *Phytophthoras* has been well studied (Beales et al., 2004; Green et al., 2021, 2025; Sims & Garbelotto, 2021). Although public gardens may have a crucial role in the epidemiology of these pathogens due to high volume of incoming stock, plant collections of diverse origin and high volume of visitors, they have not been extensively studied. Given the continuum between natural forests, gardens and the nursery trade, it is vital to better understand the role of public gardens, which may act as a reservoir of pathogens and assist the survival and spread of *Phytophthora* species.

In the framework of this project, shared protocols for sampling and detection of *Phytophthora* sp. and other oomycetes, were applied to public gardens and their nurseries across six participating countries (United Kingdom/ United States of America/ Slovenia/ Italy/ Greece/ Czech Republic). Each partner aimed to collect 40 samples from each garden and its nursery/or its supplier nurseries, over two years. Soil, plant tissue and water samples were collected and analysed using a validated metabarcoding protocol (Scibetta et al., 2012). All *Phytophthora*-positive samples were processed in the UK for Illumina sequencing of the ITS region. The *Phytophthora* classification tool <https://pypi.org/project/thapbi-pict/> (Cock et al., 2023; Green et al., 2021) was used for the bioinformatics analyses for species identification. Data from all the samples collected during the collaboration showed that *Phytophthoras* and other oomycetes were present in all sampled sites, with 51% of the samples being positive. Overall, 55 different taxa of *Phytophthora* were detected, the most frequently occurring included the complex *P. aleatoria*/ *P. alpina*/ *P. cactorum* and the species *P. multivora*, *P. nicotiana*, *P. syringae*, *P. cryptogea* and *P. pseudocryptogea*. There were differences between the top detected species among countries; however, most were present in at least two different countries. Nurseries accounted for up to 68.9% of positive samples and 46 different taxa of *Phytophthora*, confirming that nursery stock poses great risk for gardens. The important role of public gardens in the epidemiology of the pathogen was also confirmed by the 20 new *Phytophthora* spp. detections, which included new records for the country and new host associations. Furthermore, our results suggest that some plant genera may have a more important role for harboring *Phytophthora* pathogens than is currently recognised; some genera were associated with a higher number of *Phytophthora* spp. compared to the known high-risk hosts. This is alarming, as these 'lesser' hosts lie 'under the radar' but may pose risks as new species' associations and should be considered during risk analysis. Also, we identified 37 plant genera to be asymptomatic, although they were carrying more than one *Phytophthora* spp., including the regulated *P. ramorum*. Further study on the interaction between these host species and their associated *Phytophthora* species may enable us to understand if there are any patterns which could assist disease surveillance.

2.2. Project aims

The overall aim of this project was to use a coordinated approach, based on eDNA metabarcoding methodology and baiting, to gain comprehensive insight into the role of public gardens in harbouring and spreading *Phytophthora*. It aimed to assess the risks associated with *Phytophthora* species in garden systems to provide a link to our current knowledge on impact of *Phytophthora* diseases on the plant trade and natural, forest and intensive horticultural ecosystems.

The main objectives were:

- **Determine the potential risk to plant collections.** Understanding which species of *Phytophthora* are prevalent in gardens and their relationships to plant hosts for determining if there is a risk for ornamental plant collections and facilitate prompt surveillance and management.
- **Understand pathways of introduction into gardens via planting material.** Detection and characterisation of *Phytophthora* species in incoming nursery plant stock and in each garden, to determine the extent to which stock plants act as a pathway for the introduction of *Phytophthora* into gardens.
- **Enhance an existing metabarcoding method by exploring novel technologies for greater species resolution.** The current ITS1 metabarcoding method is unable to separate out some very closely related *Phytophthora* species (known as species complexes). Alternative molecular platforms were investigated to see if resolution can be improved.
- **Raising awareness of *Phytophthora* risk in garden managers and suppliers of stock plants.** The project findings were used to tailor our advice about *Phytophthora* in gardens and potential risks from incoming plant material. The advice may be used as the basis for raising awareness of symptoms, high-risk hosts and good biosecurity practice.

2.3. Description of the main activities

2.3.1. Work Package 1- Project management

The project partners met every 6 months to provide progress updates, trouble-shoot protocols, exchange ideas and insights and report results. The final meeting took place on May 13th, 2025, where partners presented their results, discussed highlights and content for the final report as well as the potential for formal publication of the data. Currently, further funding from Defra (UK) (under CSA25 - *Phytophthora* in public gardens: understanding pathways and mitigating risk (Phyto-gard)) has been secured to perform bioinformatics analyses on the collective project dataset to improve resolution of trends and associations and enable publication of the findings in scientific journal.

2.3.2. Work Packages 2 and 3- Identify *Phytophthora* diversity in public gardens and their risk to plant collections within gardens and understand the *Phytophthora* sources in ornamental nurseries leading to the introduction and spread of invasive species in gardens

Sample selection and collection

Protocols for sampling and sample processing were shared (see Annex) but partners were permitted some flexibility to enable them to operate within the constraints of their resources e.g. financial or geographical location. Within each site, 20 samples were collected (in triplicate) per year, over a two year period, at different time points from each garden and its nursery or the supplier nurseries, as not all gardens had their own nursery.

Different types of samples were collected; in the gardens, these included plant material (leaves or roots), soil samples from the rhizosphere of the selected plants as well as water samples from water bodies (e.g. streams, lakes) and puddles. In the nursery, the samples mostly consisted of flow-through water from potted plants and roots from larger specimens, as well as water from puddles within the nursery.

The selection of water samples from streams, lakes and puddles (in public paths, courtyard, near compost and waste heaps) aimed to gain a better insight of the spread patterns of the pathogen within each site. Sampling targeted both symptomatic and asymptomatic plants and, in the gardens, included sample collection from areas with suspected or proven history of *Phytophthora* diseases, as well as plant specimens of importance and national collections.

Sample analysis

Each partner country proceeded with the analysis of their own samples. In many cases, partners were able to proceed with baiting and culturing of living *Phytophthora* spp. using known *Phytophthora* protocols. To consistently obtain and amplify high quality DNA, all partners used the shared protocols (see Annex). A ~ 263 bp region of the ribosomal DNA (rDNA) internal transcribed spacer (ITS1) was amplified from each DNA sample and control samples using nested PCR with primer pairs 18Ph2F and 5.8S-1R in the first round and ITS6 and 5.8S-1R in the second round according to the protocol of Scibetta (Scibetta et al., 2012), except that proof-reading enzyme KAPA HiFi HotStart Ready-mix was used to minimise errors during the PCR reaction. All PCR-positive samples were processed into Illumina libraries collectively in the UK, sequenced on a single flow cell of an Illumina MiSeq or, following a technology change, a NextSeq 2000, at the James Hutton Institute, Dundee and sequences identified using a *Phytophthora* classifier, developed as part of the Phyto-threats project [THAPBI *Phytophthora* ITS1 Classifier Tool \(PICT\) — THAPBI PICT 0.12.0 documentation \(thapbi-pict.readthedocs.io\)](#) (Cock et al., 2023; Green et al., 2021).

2.3.3. Work Package 4- Analysis of *Phytophthora* diversity in gardens and incoming stock plants and risks posed by novel species and hybrids- exploration of alternative NGS platforms for enhanced species resolution.

The DNA samples that were positive for *Phytophthora* (and other oomycetes) by Illumina sequencing in the UK were shared with our partners in the Canadian Food Inspection Agency (CFIA) for analysis using Ion Torrent, an alternative NGS sequencing methodology. Still targeting the ITS1 region, the methodology used a single set of PCR primers compared to the Illumina nested primer method of Scibetta (2012) and resulted in an amplicon of average size 350bp that overlapped with the Scibetta amplicon of 263 bp. Pooled libraries were sequenced on the Ion S5 platform to determine if the ASV outputs could provide resolution for at least some of the *Phytophthora* species' complexes that result from the Illumina methodology. Illumina data processed through the THAPBI pipeline were reformatted and analysed using the same pipeline as the Ion Torrent data, with QIIME2 classification parameters adjusted to align with THAPBI settings.

Table 1 Samples received by the Canadian Food Inspection Agency from each country

Country	Samples Received
Slovenia	45
Italy	12
Greece	81
UK	163
USA	118
Czech Republic	97
Total	516

2.4. Main results

2.4.1. Individual project partner summaries

United Kingdom: Of the total number of positive samples, 75% were associated with *Phytophthora* spp. and 22% with other Oomycetes. A high diversity of 41 different species was found, including important tree pathogens, *Phytophthora* species complexes and unknown species of *Phytophthora* as well as *Phytophthora* spp. and other oomycetes. Garden 1 (UKG001) and nursery (UKGN001) and Garden 2 UKG002) had similar numbers of positive samples and Garden nursery 2 (UKGN002) had the least number of positives.

The most prevalent species across all sites were: *P. syringae* and *P. psychrophila*. Among the top 10 species were the species complexes *P. cryptogea/P.pseudocryptogea* and *P. aleatoria/P. alpina/P. cactorum* (which we can assume is *P. cactorum*, since the other two species have not been recorded in the UK). However, notably absent were the plant pathogens *P. austrocedri*, *P. cinnamomi* and *P. kernoviae*.

There were clear differences between sites e.g. *Phytophthora obscura*, *P. plurivora* and *P. castanetorum* were significantly more prevalent at site 2, whilst *P. cryptogea/P. pseudocryptogea* was more prevalent at site 1. Not all species were present at all four sites. Four *Phytophthoras*, notably *P. x cambivora*, *P. hibernalis*, *P. megasperma* and the quarantine pathogen, *P. ramorum* were detected in UKG002 but not UKG001, whereas UKGN001 had ten *Phytophthoras* not detected in UKGN002 including the aggressive tree pathogens, *P. ramorum*, *P. plurivora*, *P. pseudosyringae*, as well as *Phytophthora*-unknown species.

Across both sites, there were significant differences in oomycete diversity relating to sample type with samples from water bodies having the highest species diversity, followed by puddles and soil samples. Plant related samples (plant flow-through water and root samples) had the least species diversity. Overall, the species most associated with water samples (water bodies and puddles) were *Phytophthora gonapodyides*, *P. psychrophila* and *P. syringae*. There were differences even between the different types of water sample e.g. *P. lacustris* and *P. bilorbang* were commonly detected in stream water, whereas *P. syringae* was only detected in puddles. These data indicate that prioritizing good water management will help prevent disease spread throughout the gardens and nurseries and prevent 'escapes' into the environment.

P. syringae was again abundant in root samples and soil and, thus, is a cosmopolitan species requiring multiple means of risk mitigation, not just water management. It contrasts with *P. castanetorum* found only in soil and *P. cactorum* was detected in both plant flow-through water and soil.

Oomycete species (*Phytophthora* and other genera) were associated with 28 host plant genera. *Eryngium*, *Lavandula* and *Pinus* had most species associations. There were significant correlations between some species and hosts. For example, *P. castanetorum* was associated with rhododendrons and acers (root flow-through, rhizosphere soil, root samples) but was not detected in other plant related samples and was abundant in the soil sample in proximity with an acer and a rhododendron. *Phytophthora pseudocryptogea* was associated with *Camellia*, *Helleborus* and *Lavandula* and the complex *P. cryptogea*/*P. pseudocryptogea* with *Camellia* and *Lavandula*. *Phytophthora cryptogea* was associated with hellebore and *Lavandula*. Some species were associated with multiple hosts e.g. *P. psychrophila*, associated with *Chimonanthus*, *Daphne*, *Lavandula*, *Rhododendron*, *Viburnum*, the ‘acer and rhododendron’ soil sample and soil sample around an ‘unrecognised’ stump. In contrast, *P. gonapodyides* was associated only with *Sarcococca* plants and this finding was a new host association for this species. These results suggest that several key UK plant species could pose a ‘high risk’ for carrying *Phytophthoras*, including important tree pathogens. Consequently, to safeguard plant collections of those genera in public gardens, regular monitoring and testing is recommended.

Italy: The garden site did not have an in-house nursery; therefore, the plant stock samples were collected from the nurseries that traditionally provide the Botanical Garden with plants. Among the species found, with both baiting and Illumina metabarcoding, three species were more commonly detected: *P. citrophthora*, *P. nicotianae* and *P. multivora*, followed by species complexes *P. citrophthora*/*P. pseudocitrophthora*, *P. crassamura*/*P. debattistii*/*P. megasperma*, *Phytophthora occultans*/*Phytophthora pseudococcultans*. Interestingly, the top three species were associated with new hosts. These were *P. multivora* on *Calliandra haematocephala* and *Passiflora fata nivea*, *P. nicotianae* on *Rhaphiolepis indica* and *Passiflora fata nivea* and *P. citrophthora* on *Rhaphiolepis indica* and *Syzygium jambos*.

Overall, pathogens diversity was significantly higher in the garden compared to the nurseries, suggesting that either infections occur post-planting or that the garden provides more favorable conditions for pathogen persistence. This is concerning because botanical gardens frequently exchange plant material, increasing the risk of unintentional pathogen dissemination. The botanic garden had six *Phytophthora* taxonomical entities (including precisely identified species and some less-clearly distinguishable ASVs), while the first nursery had none, and the second had only *P. nicotianae*, *P. citrophthora*, and two complexes. Among the different plants that were sampled, *Passiflora fata nivea* was associated with both *P. nicotianae* and *P. multivora*, *Rhaphiolepis indica* was associated with *P. citrophthora*, *P. nicotianae*, and *P. occultans*/*P. pseudococcultans*. *Phytophthora nicotianae* and *P. citrophthora* both are generalist pathogens (have multiple hosts) and are highly pathogenic, posing a greater threat to plant health. Although the sampling design did not aim to specifically assess biosecurity practices (e.g. compost heaps, machinery), the presence of *Phytophthora* spp. in plants sourced from nurseries strongly suggests a potential pathway for pathogen introduction to the garden. This combined with the general lack of biosecurity protocols in that garden, significantly increases the risk of pathogen spread in the garden.

United States of America: The metabarcoding revealed that 53% of the samples from the two sites in California, were positive, with a total of 23 different *Phytophthora* species and species complexes. Among them, the most abundant were *P. cactorum*/*P. aleatoria*/*P. alpina*; *P. cryptogea*/*P.*

pseudocryptogea, *P. pseudocryptogea*, *Unknown Phytophthora*, *P. multivora*, *P. niederhauseri*, *P. cryptogea*, *Pythium sp.*, *P. syringae*. These results are perfectly aligned with published literature suggesting that plant stock used in restoration efforts or plantings is mostly infected by *P. cactorum*, *P. pseudocryptogea*, *P. multivora* and *P. niederhauseri* (L. Sims et al., 2019). The use of culturing in parallel with the metabarcoding analysis, confirmed the presence of *P. cactorum*, *P. pseudocryptogea* and *P. multivora* in the gardens (based on full ITS and COXI sequencing) allowing us to resolve the ambiguities of at least two complexes (namely *P. cactorum*/*P. aleatoria*/*P. alpina* which we can putatively regard as *P. cactorum*, and *P. cryptogea*/*P. pseudocryptogea* which we can putatively regard as *P. pseudocryptogea* (L. L. Sims & Garbelotto, 2021). The two most widespread Phytophthoras in restoration sites in San Francisco are *P. pseudocryptogea* and *P. multivora*.

Further, the present study reports for the second time in California the presence of *P. amnicola* in a water source. The *P. castaneorum*/*P. quercina*/*P. versiformis* complex is reported for the first time, although it is likely to be *P. quercina* (which has been found previously). Further work on delimiting the complexes to individual species will enable a better understanding on which species are actually present.

Although the regulated *P. ramorum* was detected in one nursery plant, this plant was a *Juncus patens* propagated on site. There is a history of *P. ramorum* in both the nursery and the garden but *P. ramorum* had not been detected recently. *Phytophthora thermophila* was detected only once by baiting and culturing from a water source but was not detected by metabarcoding and is a first report for the USA and California.

Czech Republic: In total 25 species, or species complexes, of the genus *Phytophthora* were recorded in samples (of which 21 in gardens and 11 in garden nursery), using the Illumina metabarcoding. The complex *Phytophthora aleatoria*/*P. alpina*/*P. cactorum*, was the most detected whilst *Phytophthora lacustris*, *P. cinnamomic*, *P. hedraiandra*/*P. x serendipita*, *P. gonapodyides*, *P. honggalleglyana*/*P. persiana*, *P. uniformis*, *Phytophthora* (unknown species), *P. castanetorum*/*P. quercina*/*P. versiformis*; *P. cryptogea*/*P. pseudocryptogea*, *P. psychrophila*, *P. syringae*, *P. x cambivora* were consistently detected in samples. Traditional baiting with rhododendron leaves was also used to isolate in all samples and resulted to the isolation of seven *Phytophthora* species: *P. cambivora*, *P. cinnamomi*, *P. gregata*, *P. hedraiandra* /*P. x serendipita*, *P. lacustris*, *P. parsiana*, and *P. pseudocryptogea*. From the comparison of the two identification methods, traditional baiting provided only a fraction of the species diversity compared to Illumina sequencing.

A concerning result of the present work is the repeated finding of *P. cinnamomi* in the garden 1 (CZG001). The pathogen was isolated from *Pieris* plants and had caused extensive damage and death of a yew (*Taxus baccata*) hedge. In the Czech Republic, *P. cinnamomi* has been repeatedly recorded in the past, especially in ornamental nurseries and retail plant stores. Its occurrence in the garden confirmed that the pathogen is able to survive in the climatic conditions of the Czech Republic and therefore it is essential to future work to focus on the management of this species. Regarding nursery sampling, the most frequently recorded species were *P. cinnamomi*, *P. gonapodyides* and *P. cryptogea/pseudocryptogea*, confirming that trade has a key role on introducing *Phytophthora* in gardens.

Continually, this work provided with first findings of different *Phytophthora* species in Czech Republic: *P. psychrophila* was detected on a withering oak in the second site (CZG002), a national park. Although

this species has been recorded once before in the country, it was in soil samples from an ornamental nursery and this is the first time that it was confirmed in a host within a garden. Further, *Phytophthora tubulina*, was recorded for the first time on asymptomatic *Rhododendron*. This species has been previously found in *Fagus sylvatica* in Austria (2010). Lastly, *P. primulae* was detected in soil samples associated with *Azalea*. In relation to water samples, two species were associated with pond samples, namely *P. lacustris* and the complex *P. honggalleglyana/persiana*.

Based on the results of this work, it is evident that Botanical gardens need to prioritise the development of biosecurity practises, especially in relation to plant procurement and quarantine of incoming stock. Additionally, strengthening biosecurity awareness of the garden staff, hygiene of tools and machinery as well as water management, will be essential to mitigate any plant health risks. Unfortunately, in both sites sampled in the present study, biosecurity practices targeting oomycetes are currently inadequate.

Slovenia: Over two years, soil, plant tissue and water samples were collected from an Arboretum (SLG001) and analysed using classical isolation methods and metabarcoding. The first year of sampling targeted areas known to have problems with *Phytophthora* diseases and it was mostly focused on the *Rhododendron* plant collections. The following year of sampling included other known *Phytophthora* hosts, such as magnolia and *Fagus sylvatica*. The most frequently detected species, through the two years of sampling, were *P. cactorum* and *P. plurivora*, which were particularly associated with *Rhododendron* plants. The first was detected in both soil and plant samples whilst *P. plurivora* was isolated all three types of samples- water, soil and plant tissues, while *P. cactorum* was often recovered from above-ground plant parts. *Rhododendron* emerged as a high-risk host, showing consistent infections with *Phytophthora* spp., highlighting its role as a potential pathogen reservoir.

Water samples yielded mostly in *P. lacustris* and *P. plurivora*, but also other *Phytophthora* species were detected, demonstrating distinct species distributions between sample types. In the water samples, traditional baiting method proved to be more effective than direct DNA extraction, likely due to low concentrations of oomycetes propagules in water. However, for soil samples Illumina metabarcoding revealed great species complexity. In total 30 different taxa in 15 total soil samples were detected. Of these 22 belonged to genus *Phytophthora*, and 1 taxon to each of the following genera: *Phytopythium*, *Pythium*, *Bremia*, *Plasmopara*, *Hyaloperonospora*, *Peronospora* and *Pseudoperonospora*. The most frequent *Phytophthora* species identified with Illumina were the *P. aleatoria/ P.alpina/ P. cactorum* complex and *P. syringae*, followed by the *P. hedraiandra/ P. x serendipita* complex, *P. plurivora* and the complex *P. acerina/P.cf. citricola* group E.

Illumina enabled the detection of six species and three species complexes, for the first time in Slovenia. These were: *P. hibernalis*, *P. obscura*, *P. psychrophila*, *P. idaei*, *P. tentaculata*, *P. tubulina*; *P. caryae/ P. pini*; *P. lactucae/ P. pseudolactucae* and *P. occultans/ P. pseudocultans*. These data suggest that *Phytophthora* pathogens are more abundant in the country, than was previously thought, and more research will enable identification of the potential impact of these detected pathogens to Slovenian gardens.

Although, it was not possible to sample nursery plant stock, it is worth mentioning that all imported plants follow a certain biosecurity procedure prior planting in the garden. All purchased plants originate from EU countries and are accompanied by the required documentation, including plant passports. All suppliers are verified, and cooperation is built on long-standing trust. The purchased

plants are first delivered to a designated depot—an outdoor concrete area equipped with irrigation—where a thorough inspection is carried out. This includes checking the plant variety, health status, and overall quality. Depending on the inspection outcome, their planting is taking place in a time-period of one to seven days. The exact timing depends on other ongoing work, weather conditions, and related factors. All activities are recorded in the system. Other biosecurity practices, include the cleaning of the garden machinery/ vehicles in specifically developed designated areas.

Phytophthora presence in both water and soil samples, not only suggests the natural movement of the pathogen but also highlights the significant phytosanitary risk that infected water and soil pose for the plant health state of the garden. Infected water or soil, in close proximity to plant collections, nursery beds, or natural vegetation increases the risk of disease outbreak, especially during favourable conditions for the pathogen e.g. heavy rainfall or irrigation overflow when the motile zoospores can be rapidly mobilized in surface water and saturated soils, facilitating the spread of the pathogen to nearby susceptible hosts. Waterlogged soils or contaminated runoff from infested zones can become powerful vectors of disease dissemination, endangering both cultivated and native plant communities. Thus, biosecurity measures including water treatment of irrigation water and barriers to eliminate overflow of water bodies, combined with good gardening practices such as good soil drainage, are essential to manage *Phytophthora* pathogens and reduce the likelihood of disease outbreaks. Additionally, *Phytophthora* diversity in samples from plant dumping sites suggests that these sites act as a reservoir for the pathogen and need to be managed appropriately to prevent the re-introduction of the pathogen to the garden. Overall, the findings emphasize the ecological breadth of *Phytophthora* in Slovenian gardens and the need for improved surveillance, biosecurity training, and management practices to protect ornamental plant collections from emerging threats.

Greece: Positive detections were obtained from both surveyed gardens, as well as from four of the sampled nurseries, indicating that all sites contributed equally to the overall diversity of isolates recovered. The 92.6 % of the positive samples were *Phytophthora* (16 different taxa) and the rest classified as other Oomycetes. The most frequently encountered species across all surveyed sites were *Phytophthora nicotianae*, *P. citrophthora*, and *P. cinnamomi*, which collectively dominated the dataset, followed by the species complexes *P. aleatoria/P. alpina/P. cactorum* and *P. honggalleglyana/ P. persiana* and the species *P. lacustris* and *P. virginiana*. The presence of both widespread pathogenic species and taxa of uncertain taxonomic status underscores not only the diversity, but also the potential epidemiological significance of *Phytophthora* populations in the studied environments.

According to Sanger sequencing and Illumina NGS results, all irrigation water samples collected from one of the public gardens resulted positively in *Phytophthora* isolates. In seven out of eight samples, different *Phytophthora* species, known to be associated with water, were identified. Those were *P. virginiana*, *P. lacustris* and *P. honggalleglyana/ P. persiana*. *Phytophthora citrophthora* was isolated from a single water sample. It is quite interesting that *P. citrophthora* as well as other water-associated species, were identified in the rhizosphere of trees scattered around the garden. These findings highlight that effective water management is a key strategy not only to limit the spread of *Phytophthora* pathogens within gardens and nurseries, but also to reduce the risk of pathogens escaping to natural ecosystems.

Phytophthora nicotianae was the most frequently isolated species from the rhizosphere of sampled plants, making it the predominant taxon detected in Greek samples. This species is a well-known and

highly aggressive pathogen with a broad host range, capable of causing root rot, stem lesions, and wilt symptoms in numerous ornamental and agricultural crops. Its dominance in the samples underscores its ecological adaptability and pathogenic potential, raising concerns about its role in both plant health decline and the wider dissemination of inoculum in cultivated and managed environments.

Identified oomycete species (*Phytophthora*, *Phytophthium* and *Globisporangium*) were isolated from 38 different host plant genera and irrigation water samples. Among the sampled host plants, *Gardenia*, *Myrtus*, and *Teucrium* exhibited the highest number of species associations, with statistically significant correlations observed between certain plant hosts and specific *Phytophthora* taxa. More specifically, *P. nicotianae* was consistently recovered from the rhizosphere of the four sampled *Gardenia* plants. Similarly, *P. cinnamomi* was identified in each of the four *Myrtus communis* plants sampled and *P. niederhauserii* was recovered from all five sampled *Teucrium* plants. Thus, it appears that there is a consistent link between these *Phytophthora* species and the plant-hosts they were isolated from.

Effective prevention and management of plant-pathogenic Oomycetes of the genus *Phytophthora* in gardens and nurseries rely on a combination of preventive and control measures. Even though diseases can be asymptomatic, it is essential to conduct thorough inspections of incoming plant stock before planting in the garden, to help avoid the introduction and establishment of pathogens. In areas that *Phytophthora* diseases are present, a set of measures is recommended, including ensuring good soil and site drainage to avoid waterlogging and water movement on site, collection and effective composting of plant debris, regular disinfection of tools, footwear and equipment and continuous monitoring for new infections and the immediate removal of diseased plants.

2.4.2. Overall summary across all countries

The results of the present project provided robust evidence that public gardens and parks host a diverse range of *Phytophthora* species and other oomycetes, which not only relate to plant collections but also to the water features of the sites. Of the total number of samples collected across the different countries (n=851), 51% were positive (n=434). In total the complex *P. aleatoria*/*P. alpina*/*P. cactorum* was ranked at the top (n=82), followed by *Phytophthora* unknown species (n=64), *P. multivora* (n=39), *P. nicotianae* and *P. syringae* (n=38), *P. cryptogea*/*P. pseudocryptogea* (n=27) (Figure 1).

Overall, 55 distinct species of *Phytophthora* were detected, with about 20 species detected only one or twice.

Figure 1 Ranking of the most detected species (based on their counts) across all sampled sites/countries. The numbers near the bar indicate the count number per species across all the Illumina (positive) analysed samples.

Different *Phytophthora* species were detected and dominated the samples in each country (Figure 2). This was not unexpected and relates to the total amount of samples in each country, the number of sampling sites (e.g. nurseries, number of gardens), the diversity of sample types and the different plant genera that were sampled. With respect to the later, the more diverse the host range that was sampled the more diverse were the *Phytophthora* identifications. For example, in the UK, where the samples related to 28 different plant genera, 41 unique oomycetes were detected, whilst in SL where the samples were associated mostly with rhododendrons and beech the number of sequences was almost half (n=19). There were differences in species presence between countries for the six most prevalent *Phytophthoras* detected (Figure2).

Figure 2 Top ranked *Phytophthora* species by country, expressed as percentages of the number of detections.

When looking at each country's top 10 species, we can observe some similarities. Most of these species were within the top of at least two countries (Table 2). *Phytophthora syringae* appears to be a cosmopolitan species detected in sampling locations in four out of the six countries, similar to the complex *P. aleatoria/ P. alpina/ P. cactorum*, followed by the complex *P. cryptogea/ P. pseudocryptogea*. Although further analysis and sampling required, there is the suggestion that the presence of some species may relate to the environmental conditions of each country. For example, *P. citrophthora* and *P. nicotianae* were ranked within the top in IT and GR and the complex *P. hedraiaandra/ P. x serendipita* in CZ and SL. Unfortunately, the lack of environmental data (which was not within the scope of the present project) as well as samples from extra locations in some countries, do not permit as simple conclusion to be drawn. For the analysis, the well-curated Thapbi-pict was used as the reference database and gave several occurrences of 'unknown' *Phytophthoras* (n=64) and other oomycetes. When these 'unknown' sequences from the UK dataset were compared with an alternative, but uncurated, database (NCBI), we found close matches (96-100% similarity) to known species. Thus, we conclude that these sequences likely represent variants of known species, which we have already detected in our samples, but are rejected by the high stringency of our sequence-matching criteria or are sequence variants that are not represented in our database.

Table 2 The most frequently detected *Phytophthora* in each country (CZ- Czech Republic, GR- Greece, IT- Italy, SL- Slovenia, UK- United Kingdom, US- United States of America). Species complexes are in bold. X indicates presence.

Phytophthora species	Country code					
	CZ	GR	IT	SL	UK	USA
<i>P. acerina</i>				X		
<i>P. aleatoria/P. alpina/P. cactorum</i>	X			X	X	X
<i>P. aleatoria</i>		X				
<i>P. alpina</i>		X				
<i>P. cactorum</i>		X				
<i>P. castanetorum/P. quercina/P. versiformis</i> ,	X				X	
<i>P. castanetorum</i>					X	
<i>P. cinnamomi</i>	X	X				
<i>P. citrophthora/P. pseudocitrophthora</i>			X			
<i>P. citrophthora</i>		X	X			
<i>P. crassamura/P. debattistii/P. megasperma</i>			X			
<i>P. cryptogea/P. pseudocryptogea</i>	X				X	X
<i>P. cryptogea</i>						X
<i>P. pseudocryptogea</i>					X	X
<i>P. gonapodyides</i>	X				X	
<i>P. hedraiondra/P. x serendipita</i>	X			X		
<i>P. honggalleglyana/P. parsiana</i>	X					
<i>P. honggalleglyana</i>		X				
<i>P. lacustris</i>	X	X				
<i>P. multivora</i>			X			X
<i>P. nicotianae</i>		X	X			
<i>P. niederhauseri</i>						X
<i>P. obscura</i>					X	
<i>P. persiana</i>		X				
<i>P. plurivora</i>				X	X	
<i>P. pseudosyringae</i>					X	
<i>P. psychrophila</i>	X				X	
<i>P. syringae</i>	X			X	X	X
<i>P. uniformis</i>	X					
<i>P. virginiana</i>		X				
<i>P. x cambivora</i>	X					
<i>P.cf. citricola group E.</i>				X		
<i>Phytophthora</i> (unknown species)	X				X	X
<i>P. occultans/P. pseudocultans</i>			X			

Another interesting result was that the detection of the regulated pathogen *P. ramorum* occurred only at low frequency in the two countries (UK and USA) where we know that the pathogen is causing important disease outbreaks and is under intensive eradication programmes. This finding might relate to the successful, on-site implementation of the plant health regulations in relation to this pathogen in both countries.

It is notable that the diversity of sampling (in relation to both host plants as well as sample type), combined with the sensitivity of the Illumina metabarcoding detection method, enabled the identification of new records of *Phytophthora*, expressed either as new findings of species for the county or as new host records (Table 3). In relation to the latter, isolation and culturing the species followed by pathogenicity tests, will confirm the role of these *Phytophthoras* and the risk they pose for the plants they were detected on.

Table 3 *Phytophthora* species new records, either as detections in the country or as association with new hosts.

<i>Phytophthora</i> species	New Host report or detection	Country
<i>P. gonapodyides</i>	<i>Sarcococca</i>	UK
<i>P. multivora</i>	<i>Calliandra haematocephala</i>	IT
<i>P. multivora</i>	<i>Passiflora fata nivea</i>	IT
<i>P. nicotianae</i>	<i>Rhaphiolepis indica</i>	IT
<i>P. nicotianae</i>	<i>Passiflora fata nivea</i>	IT
<i>P. citrophthora</i>	<i>Rhaphiolepis indica</i>	IT
<i>P. citrophthora</i>	<i>Syzygium jambos</i>	IT
<i>P. thermophila</i>	water	USA
<i>P. psychrophila</i>	<i>Quercus</i>	CZ
<i>P. tubulina</i>	<i>Rhododendron</i>	CZ
<i>P. primulae</i>	<i>Azalea</i> (soil)	CZ
<i>P. hibernalis</i>	<i>Rhododendron</i>	SL
<i>P. obscura</i>	<i>Rhododendron</i>	SL
<i>P. psychrophila</i>	<i>Fagus</i>	SL
<i>P. idaei</i>	<i>Rhododendron</i>	SL
<i>P. tentaculate</i>	<i>Rosa</i>	SL
<i>P. tubulina</i>	<i>Fagus</i>	SL
<i>P. caryae</i> / <i>P. pini</i>	<i>Rhododendron</i>	SL
<i>P. lactucae</i> / <i>P. pseudolactucae</i>	<i>Rhododendron</i>	SL
<i>P. occultans</i> / <i>P. pseudoccultans</i>	<i>Rhododendron</i>	SL

Sampling of nurseries took place in four countries and confirmed the findings of previous studies about the role of trade to *Phytophthoras* spread (Green et al., 2021, 2025; Jung et al., 2016). In the present project the percentage of nursery samples that was positive on nested PCR varied from 9.1% to 68.9%. The sampled plants did not always display disease symptoms, suggesting plant stock may act as a trojan horse for *Phytophthora* in gardens. Overall, the most detected *Phytophthoras* were the complex *P. aleatoria*/*P. alpina*/*P. cactorum*, which was ranked at the top (n=59), followed by *P. x multiformis* (n=45), *P. primulae* (n=33), the complex *P. cryptogea*/*P. pseudocryptogea* (n=32), *P. multivora* (n=30) and *P. virginiana* (n=29). In total 46 taxa of *Phytophthora* were detected through nursery sampling, of which many (n=18) were detected only once or twice. In most of the samples, the nursery- related species were also detected in the garden samples and were known to be present in the country. Despite the lack of exotic detections, the significance of the role of the horticultural trade in introducing new pathogens should not be taken lightly since there are many examples of important

cross-border introductions of pathogens associated with the plant trade. On that note, it is also concerning that the introduction of the species is not always obvious, as infections may be latent and the presence of the pathogen only noticeable a long time after plants are planted within the gardens and even when biosecurity practices are in place. Table 4 shows a list of *Phytophthora* taxa that were associated with samples from asymptomatic hosts during this project. Overall, we found 37 plant genera which displayed no symptoms of infection but carried *Phytophthoras*. Often, more than one species was present in the same plant sample, which indicates how inconspicuous *Phytophthora* infections can be and their risk. It is concerning that asymptomatic *Camellia* and *Viburnum* in the UK yielded detections of *P. ramorum*. Both genera, which are regarded as high-risk hosts of *P. ramorum* and *P. kernoviae*, are highly popular with UK gardeners. It is recommended that these genera undergo quarantine prior to entering a site and that regular visual inspections are carried out before any of the stock is introduced into important plant collections.

The focus of this project was predominantly on known, high-risk hosts and important plant specimens and collections. Interestingly, results from the UK and the USA show that some 'low-profile' hosts such as *Grevillea*, *Eryngium* and *Lavandula* are associated with many more *Phytophthora* sequences compared to the well-known hosts (e.g. rhododendron). The ability of those host genera to introduce and, potentially, fuel a diversity of *Phytophthora* diseases, increases the risk for the garden and the future of its plant collections. Additionally, considering that these genera may serve as hosts for multiple *Phytophthoras*, they may enable hybridisation between species. From a biosecurity perspective, it is worth considering if surveillance should only be carried out for known, regulated pathogens and their hosts or if risk assessments should include lesser-known hosts.

Table 4 A list of all the *Phytophthora* taxa by country that were detected in asymptomatic plant host genera. Other Oomycetes that may have been detected during Illumina have been excluded. Species' complexes are in bold.

Country	Host genus	<i>Phytophthora</i> species	
UK	<i>Eryngium</i>	<i>Phytophthora primulae</i> ; <i>Phytophthora aleatoria/ Phytophthora alpina/ Phytophthora cactorum</i>	
	<i>Acer</i>	<i>Phytophthora uliginosa</i> , <i>Phytophthora uniformis</i> , <i>Phytophthora x cambivora</i>	
	<i>Camellia</i>	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>	
	<i>Cornus</i>	<i>Phytophthora aleatoria/Phytophthora alpina/ Phytophthora cactorum</i> ; <i>Phytophthora plurivora</i> , <i>Phytophthora lacustris</i>	
	<i>Rhododendron</i>	<i>Phytophthora syringae</i> ; <i>Phytophthora castanetorum/Phytophthora quercina/Phytophthora versiformis</i> ; <i>Phytophthora psychrophila</i> , <i>Phytophthora</i> (unknown species)	
	<i>Sarcococca</i>	<i>Phytophthora gonapodyides</i>	
	<i>Toona</i>	<i>Phytophthora syringae</i>	
	<i>Viburnum</i>	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i> , <i>Phytophthora syringae</i> , <i>Phytophthora hibernalis</i> , <i>Phytophthora obscura</i> , <i>Phytophthora plurivora</i>	
	US	<i>Ceanothus</i>	<i>Phytophthora aleatoria/Phytophthora alpina/ Phytophthora cactorum</i> ; <i>Phytophthora niederhauseri</i>
		<i>Frangula</i>	<i>Phytophthora aleatoria/ Phytophthora alpina/Phytophthora cactorum; Phytophthora caryae/Phytophthora pini</i> ; <i>Phytophthora curvata</i> , <i>Phytophthora limosa</i> ; <i>Phytophthora cryptogea/ Phytophthora pseudocryptogea</i> ; <i>Phytophthora gonapodyides</i>
SL	<i>Fagus</i>	<i>Phytophthora hedraiaandra/P x serendipita</i> ; <i>Phytophthora pseudosyringae</i> , <i>Phytophthora tubulina</i> ; <i>Phytophthora aleatoria/ Phytophthora alpina/ Phytophthora cactorum; Phytophthora hedraiaandra/Phytophthora x serendipita</i> ; <i>Phytophthora syringae</i>	
	<i>Hosta</i>	<i>Phytophthora syringae</i>	
	<i>Rosa</i>	<i>Phytophthora syringae</i> , <i>Phytophthora tentaculata</i>	
CZ	<i>Azalea</i>	<i>Phytophthora aleatoria/Phytophthora alpina/ Phytophthora cactorum</i> ; <i>Phytophthora primulae</i>	
	<i>Rhododendron</i>	<i>Phytophthora tubulina</i> ; <i>Phytophthora aleatoria/Phytophthora alpina/ Phytophthora cactorum</i> ; <i>Phytophthora x pelgrandis</i>	
	<i>Taxus</i>	<i>Phytophthora castanetorum/Phytophthora quercina/Phytophthora versiformis; Phytophthora hedraiaandra/Phytophthora x serendipita; Phytophthora aleatoria/Phytophthora alpina/ Phytophthora cactorum</i> ; <i>Phytophthora psychrophila</i>	
GR	<i>Aloe</i>	<i>Phytophthora multivora</i> , <i>Phytophthora nicotianae</i> , <i>Phytophthora niederhauseri</i>	
	<i>Citrus</i>	<i>Phytophthora citrophthora/Phytophthora pseudocitrophthora</i> ; <i>Phytophthora mediterranea</i> , <i>Phytophthora nicotianae</i> ; <i>Phytophthora caryae/Phytophthora pini/Phytophthora curvata/ Phytophthora limosa</i> ; <i>Phytophthora multivora</i>	
	<i>Dianella</i>	<i>Phytophthora heterospora/ Phytophthora palmivora</i>	
	<i>Elaeagnus</i>	<i>Phytophthora citrophthora/Phytophthora pseudocitrophthora</i>	
	<i>Eremophila</i>	<i>Phytophthora multivora</i> , <i>Phytophthora nicotianae</i> ; <i>Phytophthora citrophthora/Phytophthora pseudocitrophthora</i>	
	<i>Euphorbia</i>	<i>Phytophthora melonis</i> , <i>Phytophthora pistaciae</i> , <i>Phytophthora nicotianae</i>	
	<i>Ficus</i>	<i>Phytophthora nicotianae</i>	
	<i>Gardenia</i>	<i>Phytophthora nicotianae</i> ; <i>Phytophthora honggalleglyana/Phytophthora persiana</i> ; <i>Phytophthora virginiana</i>	
	<i>Lavandula</i>	<i>Phytophthora citrophthora/Phytophthora pseudocitrophthora</i> ; <i>Phytophthora nicotianae</i>	
	<i>Limoniastrum</i>	<i>Phytophthora nicotianae</i> ; <i>Phytophthora citrophthora/Phytophthora pseudocitrophthora</i>	
	<i>Metrosideros</i>	<i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> , <i>Phytophthora nicotianae</i>	
	<i>Myrtus</i>	<i>Phytophthora nicotianae</i> , <i>Phytophthora multivora</i> , <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i>	
	<i>Nandina</i>	<i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i>	
	<i>Olea</i>	<i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> ; <i>Phytophthora heterospora/Phytophthora palmivora</i>	
	<i>Phillyrea</i>	<i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i>	
	<i>Pistacia</i>	<i>Phytophthora melonis</i> , <i>Phytophthora pistaciae</i>	
	<i>Pittosporum</i>	<i>Phytophthora niederhauseri</i>	
	<i>Rhamnus</i>	<i>Phytophthora niederhauseri</i> , <i>Phytophthora nicotianae</i>	
	<i>Rhaphiolepis</i>	<i>Phytophthora aleatoria/Phytophthora alpina/Phytophthora cactorum; Phytophthora citrophthora/Phytophthora pseudocitrophthora</i> ; <i>Phytophthora multivora</i>	
	<i>Rosa</i>	<i>Phytophthora multivora</i> ; <i>Phytophthora citrophthora/ Phytophthora pseudocitrophthora</i> ; <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i>	
	<i>Rosmarinus</i>	<i>Phytophthora citrophthora/Phytophthora pseudocitrophthora</i> ; <i>Phytophthora nicotianae</i>	
	<i>Stipa</i>	<i>Phytophthora melonis</i> , <i>Phytophthora pistaciae</i>	
	<i>Teucrium</i>	<i>Phytophthora multivora</i> , <i>Phytophthora niederhauseri</i> , <i>Phytophthora nicotianae</i> , <i>Phytophthora melonis</i> , <i>Phytophthora pistaciae</i> ; <i>Phytophthora aleatoria/ Phytophthora alpina/Phytophthora cactorum; Phytophthora heterospora/Phytophthora palmivora</i>	

2.4.3. Comparison of technologies for *Phytophthora* species resolution

Illumina and Ion Torrent generally showed good concordance of species detection in that both platforms detected 19 / 28 of the total *Phytophthora* species (Figure 3). Ion Torrent identified three species not detected by Illumina i.e. *P. sansomeana*, *P. thermophila* and *P. personensis*, likely a reflection of their low read abundance and distribution in the samples, while six species were unique to Illumina, including high reads of *P. multivora* and *P. syringae*, reflecting differences in reference database content and sequence variant representation.

Figure 3 Heat map illustrating species distribution across countries and sequencing technologies. Country codes: CZ- Czech Republic, GR- Greece, IT- Italy, SL- Slovenia, UK- United Kingdom, US- United States

Despite initial expectations, Ion Torrent did not improve resolution within species complexes. The ITS1 amplicon length was not substantially longer than that of Illumina, limiting the ability to resolve the closely related taxa. In fact, the *P. lateralis* complex found in Ion Torrent at high reads (Figure 4) is resolved well in Illumina as *P. ramorum* or *P. lateralis*. Cluster validation using phylogenetic analysis confirmed the tight genetic relationships within several complexes, highlighting the limitations of short read ITS1 sequences for species-level resolution. These observations point to the continued need for improved methods to resolve closely related taxa.

To enhance resolution, future work will explore the use of alternative markers such as *rps10* or long-read sequencing technologies like MinION. The use of dedicated PCR and post-PCR preparation areas

Figure 4 Dendrogram showing relationships within the *P. lateralis* species cluster

and synthetic G-block controls in plate set-up (as were used in Illumina in this study) are highly recommended to reduce contamination risk, especially important with low read numbers and high sensitivity of the methods (Cock et al., 2023; Green et al., 2021).

2.5. Conclusions and recommendations to stakeholders and policymakers

This project provided strong evidence that public gardens and their supplying nurseries harbour a range of *Phytophthora* species and other Oomycetes. The diversity of those species was associated with the diversity of host plants, the presence of water features and, in some cases, poor biosecurity practices. This project has confirmed that incoming plant stock to gardens poses a high risk of introducing these pathogens to the gardens. The establishment of pathogens into gardens following planting leads to disease outbreaks and puts valuable plant collections at risk. As most *Phytophthora* species are not quarantine-regulated organisms, general good management practices and hygiene are essential to minimise their spread. The present work has demonstrated the ever-expanding host ranges of *Phytophthoras* and, as a result, our perception about high-risk hosts needs to be re-evaluated. At present, the term ‘high-risk host’ is used for plant species that are hosts of regulated pathogens. Here, we provide a different angle on the use of the term ‘high-risk host’; a plant could pose high risk depending on the number of different *Phytophthora* spp. that it is associated with, irrespective of their regulated status. If a host is associated with multiple *Phytophthoras* (especially if these species are polyphagous species), it will increase the risk of disease outbreaks. Therefore, risk assessments of such hosts could be of benefit for the horticultural industry. Considering that once the pathogen has been introduced and established in a garden its elimination is almost impossible, the role of biosecurity is even more important. Across all sampling sites, an extremely limited number of gardens implemented good biosecurity principles. In many cases there were procedures in place, however a joined-up consideration of the risks during the entire process was lacking: from plant procurement, border control (plant reception areas), plant holding period (plant quarantine), post-

planting inspections and risk mitigation plans. Additionally, even in those gardens for which biosecurity protocols were in place, the day-to-day activities need further improvement e.g. waste compost heaps near to the nursery and quarantine area represent a risk.

It was beyond the scope of this project to study how implementation of biosecurity practices affected *Phytophthora* detections. However, through this multi-country collaboration and its interaction with horticulture stakeholders, some interesting trends were observed which may be worth future study. The ability to enforce good plant health practices in the gardens tended to reflect the level of available funding and the overall plant health understanding at the country-level. Not all countries had the financial capacity to support the biosecurity development necessary for effectively mitigating most risks. Therefore, highlighting a 'minimum' and low-cost best practice standard, which can be applied regardless of the financial capacity of each country, would be of benefit.

2.6. Benefits from trans-national cooperation

From a scientific perspective, the trans-national collaboration enabled us to apply shared protocols in our investigations to obtain a more robust result for our research objectives/questions. During our regular meetings, we were able to exchange ideas, experiences and discuss topics around our experimental approaches and methodologies, all of which proved to be very important for improving our research (both individually and as a group). A much more representative understanding and shared perspective on *Phytophthora* presence in public gardens and the risks they pose was developed as a result. The overall results enabled us to understand trends in relation to prevalent species, risky host plants and, importantly, provided very strong evidence linking pathogens in plant nurseries with pathogens in public gardens. Lastly, the experience from this trans-national cooperation has formed the basis for new collaborations and a joint publication.

3. Outreach

3.1. Article(s) for publication in journals

We currently have further funding (DEFRA, UK) for BIOSSE statistics team to perform an in-depth analysis of the Illumina metabarcoding data from across all the partners to further unpick relationships between species in nurseries and gardens. Results will be written up as a journal article with all the partners as co-authors.

3.2. Grey literature

A comprehensive report focusing on the UK results and their implications on Phytophthora management in the RHS gardens has been shared with Defra and the RHS.

3.3. Events

This project has been the subject of national and international conferences. In total the project was represented 11 times, including at the 11th IUFRO meeting *Phytophthora* in Forest and Natural Ecosystems (New Zealand, 2024) as well as the 17th Congress of the Mediterranean Phytopathological Union (Italy, 2025).

4. Open Euphresco data

Not applicable.

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Annex: Shared sampling protocols

Type of samples and sample collection

Soil samples

Soil samples were collected using a clean soil-corer from around the base of plants growing in the garden. Approximately 100 g of the soil samples was placed into a sealable plastic bag and the soil stored at 5 °C for no more than a few days before being sent to the FR laboratory where samples were stored at -20 °C before DNA extraction. Soil sampling tools were cleaned with Propellar™ or other approved disinfectant between samples.

Water samples

Each water sample was collected in triplicate, as previously described (Green et al., 2021). We used two different controls: a lab control and field control, which was tap water from the laboratory and mains water from the site, respectively, that was used to wash the equipment between samples after sterilisation to check for potential carry-over. Water flow-through samples were obtained in nurseries by standing groups of pots of the same plants in a tray, watering the soil and leaving the water to percolate for 30 mins. All water samples were pre-filtered through muslin cloth and pumped through a 47 mm diameter mixed cellulose ester filter (Millipore Sigma, Massachusetts, USA) of 1.2 µm pore size held in a 47 mm polycarbonate in-line filter holder (Pall Corporation, New York, USA) using a pressure sprayer (Hozelock, Birmingham, England). Up to three filters per sample were collected (depending on the rate at which filters blocked) and placed in a 15 ml buffer tube containing 8 ml of Longmire lysis buffer (100 mM Tris, 100 mM EDTA, 10 mM NaCl, 0.5 % SDS). Buffer tubes containing filters were stored at 5-10 °C (in a cool box in the field) before being sent to the laboratory where they were stored at room temperature for up to a week before DNA extraction or were aliquoted (1.5 ml) and stored at -20°C prior to DNA extraction.

Roots

Plants were removed from pots and triplicate samples of discoloured roots were collected into small khaki seed envelopes within small ziplock bags. At FR, the envelopes of roots were frozen at -80°C prior to overnight desiccation in a Christ™ Alpha 1-2 LD Plus freeze dryer. Samples were ground in a bead mill, 350mg weighed, followed by freezing prior to DNA extraction.

DNA Extraction

For all water samples, DNA was extracted from 1.5 ml aliquots of the Longmire's buffer sample containing filters using the DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit (Qiagen Sciences, Germantown, MD, USA) according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Soil samples were stored at -20 °C before being oven dried in aluminium trays at 32 °C for approximately a week depending on water content. Dried soil was stirred thoroughly and

ground using 1.5 cm ball bearings in 50 ml canisters with a Retsch MM400 mill. DNA was extracted from three x 250 mg subsamples using the PowerSoil® Pro DNA isolation kit (Qiagen) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Post-DNA extraction clean-up was carried out using the Zymo DNA Clean & Concentrator™ according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Roots (40mg) were extracted using the DNAeasy Plant Pro (Qiagen).

PCR of samples for metabarcoding

A ~ 263 bp region of the ribosomal DNA (rDNA) internal transcribed spacer (ITS1) was amplified from each DNA sample and control samples using nested PCR with primer pairs 18Ph2F and 5.8S-1R in the first round and ITS6 and 5.8S-1R in the second round according to the protocol of Scibetta (Scibetta et al., 2012), except that proof-reading enzyme KAPA HiFi HotStart ReadyMix was used to minimise errors during the PCR reaction.